

The TOXIN knowledge graph: Supporting animal-free risk assessment of cosmetics

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Abstract

The prohibition on animal testing for cosmetic ingredients in the European Union has sped up the changeover to assessing chemicals' safety without animals. Although validated New Approach Methodologies (NAMs) exist for local toxicity, complex endpoints like repeated-dose systemic toxicity still lack complete replacement. Next-Generation Risk Assessment (NGRA) has therefore emerged as a human-relevant, exposure-led framework. However, its success heavily depends on the availability and quality of historical data. *In silico*, read-across, and other non-testing approaches rely on existing data, making the concept of "garbage in, garbage out" a critical challenge. One of the richest yet most underused sources of regulatory data is the Scientific Committee on Consumer Safety (SCCS). SCCS opinions describe toxicological results, mechanistic insights, uncertainty discussions, and regulatory decisions on cosmetic ingredients. Still, these documents are narrative PDFs with inconsistent formats across decades and committees, making them not machine-readable nor easily searchable, hindering data reusability. To address this, we developed the TOXIN Knowledge Graph (TOXIN KG), a semantic, ontology-based platform that transforms SCCS opinions into structured, interoperable, and queryable data in RDF. TOXIN KG combines an abundance of information including chemical identifiers (SMILES), reliability scoring (ToxRTool), biological ontologies, and OECD QSAR Toolbox predictions to allow the systematic and thorough exploration of the safety of cosmetic ingredients. Using TOXIN KG, we identified cosmetics associated with liver toxicity and transparently selected HC Yellow No. 13 for an NGRA case study. In parallel, the TOXIN Analyzer was developed to automate extraction of PDF content into machine-readable tables (CSV). TOXIN KG demonstrates that unlocking of previous regulatory data can facilitate the NAM-based hazard identification, the *in silico* modeling, and the NGRA confidence building. In the end, it leads to risk assessment that is reproducible, transparent, and totally animal-free.